

Fabrication of Gas-Diffusion Electrodes for CO₂ Conversion: Effect of Sputtering Parameters

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Abstract

Low-temperature electrochemical CO₂ reduction (ECO₂R) is proven to be one of several promising strategies to valorise CO₂ through its conversion into value-added products and fuels. In fact, it is the only alternative for the direct conversion of CO₂ into ethylene, with Cu being the only metal exhibiting any selectivity and activity towards the conversion of CO₂ to C₂ products. However, developing functional materials as electrocatalysts and electrodes is imperative to achieve industrially relevant performances and efficiencies. In this sense, besides the necessary improvements in terms of decreased energy consumption at high current densities, it is important to improve the faradaic efficiencies towards desired carbon products, while hindering the competitive hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). Gas-diffusion electrodes (GDE) based on carbon paper and cloth are the standard approach used in ECO₂R; however, during operation, the surface properties (e.g. wettability) of such carbon-based GDEs might change, ultimately favouring the HER and, thus, affecting the efficiency of the process. As alternative, few examples proposing the use of PTFE-based porous structures on which metallic Cu layers are used as both conductive support and catalyst[1], have demonstrated to be a promising approach to avoid the use of carbon-based electrodes. In the context of SOLDAC project, we have developed a systematic study on the deposition conditions of sputtered Cu on PTFE structures. Therefore, we have observed that these physical features have a significant effect not only on the electrical conductivity of the electrodes, but also on the ECO₂R performance towards specific products, as show in Figure 1. As observed, different pressure conditions during sputtering modify the texture of the surface and might induce crack formation. This variation leads to different operation cathode potentials, that can decrease up to 400 mV at 200 mA·cm⁻² in the electrodes with smoother surfaces, while the product distribution is also significantly affected by the current density on electrodes with varied physical properties. Finally, faradaic efficiencies to ethylene >50% are attained with these developed electrodes at cathode potentials of -1 to -1.2 V_{RHE}, showing the potential of as-prepared GDEs based on Cu-PTFE.

Keywords: CO₂ conversion, electrocatalysis, ethylene, copper.

Fig. 1 – Variation of faradaic efficiencies with current density with sputtered materials prepared under different aperture conditions (left), and SEM images showing the microstructure variation of Cu-sputtered samples on PTFE membranes.

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References:

- [1] Kim, C., Bui, J.C., Luo, X., Cooper, J.K., Kusoglu, A., Weber, A.Z., Bell, A.T., *Tailored catalyst microenvironments for CO₂ electroreduction to multicarbon products on copper using bilayer ionomer coatings*, Nature Energy 6, 1026–1034, 2021.